

Digital Story Time (DST) User Experience Improvement Report

March 2025

eKitabu

inABLE
powering potential

Study commissioned by eKitabu and inAble.org

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Acknowledgements

James Angoye and the FoVET Research & Consultancy team (Catherine Egunza, Benedict Mbuvi and Caroline Kitheka) would like to express our deepest appreciation to inABLE and eKitabu teams that accompanied us to the field. We also acknowledge all the other staff who were involved in this user experience research for eKitabu's Digital Story Time innovation and ensured that the report brings the best possible value.

Special gratitude to the two schools (Kedowa School for the Deaf and Tumutumu School for the Deaf) and the parents that participated in the user experience research. Also the 13 Schools for the Deaf whose learners and parents participated in the survey. We appreciate the team of 174 project participants (learners, parents, heads of institutions, Board of Management, teachers, and DST teachers) who consented to participate and give valuable information that shaped the findings, recommendations, and conclusions of this report.

Executive Summary

This report synthesizes findings from 174 participants that include 51 users who participated in the user experience research conducted at Kedowa and Tumutumu Schools for the Deaf, including focus group discussions with learners, teachers, and parents, as well as key informant interviews with school headteachers. A further 123 participants responded to the surveys for learners (73) from Project Schools, NEW schools (20) and parents (30). The research reveals that DST is a highly valued educational tool with significant positive impact on Deaf learners' engagement, literacy development, and family communication across its three delivery platforms: (1) preloaded classroom version, (2) YouTube version, and (3) scheduled television programming.

Key findings include:

Strong Engagement with Visual Content: Learners consistently show high engagement with DST's visual storytelling approach across all platforms, with varying experiences based on delivery channel. Learner engagement with DST stories was notable, with 57.5% of learners consistently finishing the videos and 32.9% expressing a desire for more content.

Family Communication Bridge: DST serves as a valuable tool for enabling family communication and sign language learning at home, with television and YouTube versions playing particularly important roles. Parental/guardian feedback consistently highlighted the positive impact of DST on child development, with 93% reporting some level of improvement.

Platform-Specific Challenges: Each delivery channel presents unique challenges, from device limitations in classrooms to fixed scheduling on television to navigation issues on YouTube. Further, there is limited device availability for use of the classroom version, internet connectivity issues for YouTube access, and fixed scheduling constraints for television broadcast restrict consistent DST utilization.

The recommendations in this report focus on platform-specific improvements to make DST more effective, engaging, and accessible across its three delivery channels while maintaining a consistent learning experience.

1.0 About Digital Story Time

Digital StoryTime (DST) is an innovation by eKitabu that provides accessible digital content. It was launched in 2020 to respond to the remote learning needs of learners with disabilities during COVID-19. Specifically, sign language video storybooks with closed captions were broadcasted by the government digital TV channel in Kenya - Edu TV.

Although Digital StoryTime was targeted at users who are Deaf or hard of hearing, the stories also included human narrated audio so that even learners who have difficulty seeing the screen will be able to listen. Kenyan Sign Language (KSL) is used to ensure it is context appropriate for Kenya. Even without knowledge of sign language, all children can benefit from the DST content as it is signed slowly to facilitate language acquisition, has colorful illustrations and closed captions. Each episode is followed by comprehension questions and vocabulary lessons and it includes a tie-in to interactive online learning resources.

2.0 Research Methodology

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2.1 The Approach

The User Experience research was conducted by a team from FoVET Research & Consultancy led by James Angoye. This was supported by staff from inABLE and eKitabu. A total of 174 participants were part of the study with 51 being part of the actual user experience research and 123 participants responding to the perception survey.

The user experience research was conducted at two schools: Kedowa School for the Deaf (Kericho County) and Tumutumu School for the Deaf (Nyeri County) in March 2025 and consisted of focus group discussions, key informant interviews and one-on-one interactions with learners. The survey data was collected from 13 Schools for the Deaf across Kenya led by eKitabu staff in February and March 2025.

The user experience data was collected through a total of 51 users:

- Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with deaf learners (n=12)
- FGDs with teachers (n=8)
- FGDs with parents/guardians (n=13)
- Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) with headteachers (n=2)
- One on one interactions with learners on DST (n=16)

The perception survey data was collected from 93 learners and 30 parents:

- 73 learners from ongoing project schools (presented as “Project schools” in this report)
- 30 parents from ongoing project schools
- 20 learners from schools not yet implementing DST program (presented as “NEW schools” in this report)

The findings of this study are heavily drawn from the user experience one on one interaction through key informan interviews, focus group discussions, and one-on-one interactions of 51 participants from Kedowa and Tumutumu Schools for the deaf. The perception surveys from parents and learners in 13 other schools are used to triangulate some of the findings. The steps taken for the one-on-one user experience feedback with learners were partiipatory and learner friendly (see annex 1).

One-on-One User Experience Assessment Process:

The user experience research employed a structured 5-part methodology designed specifically for young deaf learners, conducted as individual 15-20 minute sessions with sign language interpreter support. Each session utilized child-friendly, visual assessment tools including:

- (1) **Emoji Reactions** - learners selected emotional responses (happy, sad, confused, excited, bored) to DST elements using picture cards;
- (2) **"Show Me How" Activity** - hands-on demonstration of DST navigation and feature identification using loaded tablets;
- (3) **Sticker Ranking** - intensity measurement where learners distributed 5 star stickers across DST components to indicate preference strength;
- (4) **Drawing Activity** - creative expression exercise capturing learner interests and suggestions through artwork - they alternatively had the option of explaining rather than drawing; and
- (5) **Choice Questions** - binary preference selection using visual comparisons for story length, viewing context, content type, and device preferences.

This multi-modal approach bypassed traditional language barriers while generating both quantitative metrics (emoji distributions, sticker counts, choice selections) and qualitative insights (behavioral observations, explanations, creative expressions), enabling comprehensive assessment of user experience across cognitive, emotional, and behavioral dimensions of DST interaction.

2.2 User Personas and Evolution

The study notes the evolution of the target groups of the Digital Story Time content (called personas for purposes of user experience). These personas gave the context of the findings with the primary persona being the early years Deaf learners

2.2.1 Original Core Persona: Early Years Deaf Learners

DST was originally developed with a primary focus on early years deaf learners (ages 3-9) in classroom settings. This core persona has several key characteristics:

- Limited or developing sign language skills
- Highly visual learning style
- Teacher-dependent for technology navigation
- Need for foundational vocabulary and concepts
- Classroom-based learning as primary context

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- Classroom-based learning as primary context

2.2.2 Evolving User **Personas**

Our research reveals that DST usage has naturally expanded beyond the original target audience, creating several additional user personas that must now be considered:

a) **Independent Older Deaf Learners (Ages 10-15)**

- More advanced sign language proficiency
- Greater desire for content control and independence
- More sophisticated content interests (people-centered rather than animal stories)
- Capable of independent navigation on YouTube with proper interface design
- "I can use it and help others" (Tumutumu learner R3)

b) **Families of Deaf Children**

- Mixed hearing/deaf family members
- Variable sign language skills (67% of parents reported having only basic sign language skills, and 20% reported having no sign language knowledge at all)
- Home-based co-viewing as primary context
- Learning sign language alongside child
- "My child is the one who teaches me the sign language" (Tumutumu parent R4)

c) **Teachers with Variable Technology Comfort**

- Need for curriculum integration
- Classroom management requirements
- Variable technical skills

"For me, because I'm advocating for English... I wish we could have a different English story"
(Kedowa teacher R1)

Table 1: User Persona Characteristics Comparison

Persona	Age Range	Sign Language Skills	Technology Independence	Content Preferences	Primary Context
Early Years Deaf Learners	3-9 years	Limited / Developing	Teacher-dependent	Animal stories, simple vocabulary	Classroom
Independent Older Learners	10-15 years	Advanced	Can help others (9.6%)	People-centered stories	Mixed
Families of Deaf Children	Adult	67% basic, 20% none	Variable	Co-viewing, learning together	Home
Teachers	Adult	Professional	Variable tech comfort	Curriculum integration	Classroom

2.2.3 Design Implications

While expanding to serve these evolving personas, DST must maintain its core strengths for early years learners. Key considerations include:

- **Preserving simplicity** for youngest users while adding optional complexity for older learners
- **Supporting learning progression** from basic to advanced content
- **Facilitating independent** usage for older children while maintaining teacher-facilitated options
- **Enabling family participation** without requiring advanced sign language knowledge

The recommendations in this report aim to address the needs of all user personas while remaining true to DST's foundational purpose of supporting early years deaf education.

3.0 Findings on Platform Usage & Preference Overview

This section discusses the overall findings from the perception surveys and the channels used to deliver DST for learning purposes.

3.1. Overall findings from the Perception Survey

The perception survey from the learners in 13 different schools generated the following findings.

3.1.1 DST Use Support

Learners from Project schools reported a significant degree of independence in DST video usage, with 43.8% reporting they can use it by themselves. However, a substantial portion required assistance, either occasionally (21.9%) or consistently (20.5%). 9.6% of learners reported they can use DST and help others. The learners from the NEW schools reported more independence in using DST (with 50% reporting “daily” use) compared to those from Project schools (21% reporting “daily” use).

Teachers emerge as the primary source of support for DST usage (35.6%), followed by family members (parent/guardian 13.7%, sibling 5.5%). Notably, 17.8% of learners reported needing no help at all.

Sources of DST assistance vary with age, indicating changing support needs. Younger learners (8-11 years) rely most on teachers (50%) and parents (25%), with very few (5%) reporting no help needed. The 12-16 year group still relies on teachers (33.3%) but shows a significant increase in those needing no help (22.2%), with friends offering some support (8.3%). Older learners (17-20 years) are more independent, with 23.5% reporting no help needed, while teachers (23.5%) and friends (17.6%) remain key sources of assistance; siblings offer more help in this group (11.8%), while parental support is less common.

3.1.2 DST Interaction Frequency

DST usage frequency varied significantly, with "a few times a week" being the most common (55% overall). Daily usage was reported by 21%, while less frequent usage accounted for 25%. Interestingly, the oldest learners (17-20 years) showed the highest rate of daily usage (35%) compared to younger groups.

Table 2: Project Vs NEW Schools Comparison on DST related Interaction Metrics

Metric	Project Schools (n=73)	NEW Schools (n=20)	Key Insight
Daily Usage	21%	50%	Higher intrinsic motivation in NEW schools
Device Availability	97% have devices	42% have devices	Major access gap
TV Preference	Majority across ages	100% boys, 90% girls	Consistent platform preference
Independence	42% self-sufficient	55% self-sufficient	Higher independence in NEW schools

These findings highlight that non-implementing schools show higher engagement or potential to engage with DST related videos.

3.1.3 Parental Support and Language Barriers

The survey reveals significant challenges in parental support for DST usage:

Sign Language Proficiency Gap: Among the 30 parents who responded, a majority (67%) reported having only basic sign language skills, and 20% reported having no sign language knowledge at all. Only a small fraction (14%) reported fluency or intermediate skills.

Impact on Support: The ability to support child usage varied, with parents/guardians with no sign language knowledge reporting the highest challenges (100%). Difficulty of use was least reported among basic users (10%), but time constraints varied across groups.

Internet Access Limitations: Limited internet access emerged as a significant challenge, with 73% of parents reporting "regular but limited" access and 13.3% reporting "no internet" access. Consistent internet access was reported by only a small fraction (7%).

3.1.4 Learner Engagement and Content Preferences

The survey data reveals important patterns in how learners engage with DST content:

Completion Rates: Learner engagement with DST stories was notably high, with 92% of learners consistently finishing the videos. Furthermore, 36% expressed a desire for more content. Gender analysis revealed a slight variation, with girls showing a marginally higher tendency to always finish stories and seek more content.

Content Format Preferences: The majority of learners (51%) preferred comprehensive video content, including signing, pictures, words, and animations. This preference was slightly more pronounced among girls, while boys showed a higher preference for signing-focused content. Interestingly, the preference for comprehensive content decreased with age, while the preference for signing focus increased.

Enhancement Suggestions: Learners emphasized enhancing content engagement through songs, dance, and vocabulary (56%), and adding more storylines (29%). Age-specific analysis indicated variations in desired content engagement. Younger learners wanted more pictures (75%) whereas older learners wanted more games (60-65%).

3.1.5 Parental Perceived Benefits and Challenges

Parents reported a range of benefits and challenges related to DST:

Developmental Impact: Parental/guardian feedback consistently highlighted the positive impact of DST on child development. An overwhelming 93% of parents reported some level of improvement. Notably, 100% of parents reported increased interest in learning, and nearly all (98%) reported improvements in overall development, concentration, knowledge/engagement, and independent learning.

Key Benefits: Across all parent groups, there was universal agreement (100% agreement) on DST's effectiveness in promoting learning and independent learning. However, parents with different sign language proficiency levels emphasized different benefits. Parents with no sign language knowledge prioritized academic improvement (83.3%), fluent parents valued DST primarily for entertainment (50%), while those with basic or intermediate skills placed highest importance on fostering independence (60%) and strengthening family relationships (85%).

Primary Challenges: Internet connectivity emerged as the most pressing concern (40%), followed by device availability (30%), desire for more stories (20%), and need for parental sign language training (10%).

Below are the three DST delivery channels that are currently used by the different users.

3.2.3. DST Content broadcast on Television channels:

- Fixed schedule limits control but increases accessibility
- Often watched with family members
- No pause/replay capability

"The KSL episodes are very short time, they show for less than an hour for each episode" (Tumutumu parent R7)

3.3 Key UX Findings by Platform

This section discusses the overall findings from the perception surveys and the channels used to deliver DST for learning purposes.

Similar findings were noted when the learners were asked to give star ratings on different elements of DST based on their satisfaction levels

3.3.1. Preloaded Classroom **Version Experience**

3.3.1.1 High Student Engagement Despite Implementation Challenges

Finding: Despite access limitations, learners demonstrate exceptional engagement with DST content in classroom settings with evidence of knowledge retention and application.

Evidence:

- High motivation observed: *Teachers report learners "can interact with gadgets from morning to evening" (Kedowa Teacher R1)*
- Active engagement: *" First, I introduce the topic using traditional books. Then, we watch a related digital story. Afterward, I ask students to narrate what they understood in sign language" (Tumutumu teacher R2)*
- Post-viewing activities demonstrate impact: *"Sometimes after watching...they come in front of the class. They just start role playing" (Kedowa Teacher)*

Impact: Despite implementation challenges, classroom DST creates high engagement and observable learning outcomes when accessible.

3.3.1.2 Limited Device Access Creates Learning Bottlenecks

Finding: Schools have insufficient devices to allow all learners direct interaction with DST content, teachers use projectors or rotate limited devices among learners.

Evidence:

- Limited devices create access bottlenecks: *"We do not have gadgets for the learners. We use projector" (Tumutumu teacher R3)*
- Teacher-controlled interface limits learner interaction: *"Only teacher do the operation on the gadget" (Tumutumu teacher R2)*
- School infrastructure challenges: *"Power outage, school doesn't have a backup" (Tumutumu teacher R1)*
- Device sharing affects usage: *"The way maybe the timetable has been set, you might find that there are two classes which need to use the gadgets at the same time and they are not enough" (Tumutumu Headteacher)*

Impact: The classroom implementation model limits independent learner interaction with DST content and creates access bottlenecks.

3.3.1.3 Current Content Does Not Fully Align with Curriculum Needs

Finding: Teachers struggle to integrate DST content into their curriculum because it lacks structured pedagogical frameworks that align with the lower grade teaching approaches. Further, the curriculum does not respond to higher grade learners needs.

Evidence:

- Teachers struggle with grade-level appropriateness: "I cannot use DST in upper class" (Tumutumu teacher R5) - mostly because the content is not always appropriate.
- Content structure doesn't match teaching needs: "In addition, DST does not have enough sign-exact English content. While we appreciate that DST includes Kenyan Sign Language (KSL), our students need materials that match written English structure to improve literacy" (Tumutumu teacher) and "there is no part where 'I do'" (Kedowa teacher R3)
- Teachers use DST selectively: "I use DST when I am introducing a topic. Then I switch off the device and then you go ahead" (Kedowa teacher R1)

Impact: Current classroom version is not fully aligned with curriculum needs or structured teaching approaches, limiting its integration into daily lessons. The teachers feel that the DST would be useful if expanded to also target higher grades in the schools where it is implemented to enhance its usefulness. The teachers also feel that DST can also be utilized as a tool to improve literacy through more use of Sign Exact English.

3.3.2. YouTube Version Experience

The following is a summary of some of the findings on the prerequisites for learners to have a YouTube version experience to access DST.

Table 3: Internet Access vs Device Ownership

Resource	Availability	Impact on YouTube Access
Smartphones	90% have	High potential
Consistent Internet	6.7% have	Major bottleneck
Regular but Limited Internet	73.3% have	Occasional access only
No Internet	13.3% have	Complete exclusion

This highlights the critical disconnect between device ownership and connectivity.

3.3.2.1 YouTube Facilitates Valuable Family Learning Experiences

Finding: When available, the YouTube version enables important co-viewing experiences that foster family communication and sign language learning among hearing family members.

Evidence:

- Co-viewing behavior: *"When we are watching with the kid, we pause, and then we repeat the signing"* (Tumutumu parent R5)
- Learning transfer: *"After watching the DST, the child will ask you your name, write it and then sign it"* (Kedowa parent R6)
- Parent-child role reversal: *"Sometimes, my child is the one who teaches me the sign language"* (Tumutumu parent R4)

Impact: YouTube version facilitates family learning, with control features supporting engagement.

3.3.2.2 Navigation and Access Barriers Limit Independent Use

Finding: Most Deaf learners and their families struggle to independently access and navigate DST content on YouTube due to connectivity, device, and interface challenges.

Evidence:

- Limited independent navigation ability: Only 2 of 16 learners interviewed one to one could independently navigate DST on YouTube
- Internet connectivity issues: 73% of the 30 surveyed parents have only occasional internet (typically mobile data)
- Device constraints: Survey data shows 19 out of 73 learners (26%) surveyed have no devices at home

Impact: YouTube version offers flexibility but faces significant access and navigation barriers for many potential users.

3.3.2.3 Content Discovery Is Challenging on YouTube Platform

Finding: The current organization of DST content on YouTube makes it difficult for Deaf users to navigate through the content without text-based search capabilities.

Evidence:

- Selective viewing possible: *"I have downloaded them on my phone, and with that, I don't always have to have bundles for them to watch"* (Kedowa parent R3)
- Content discovery is challenging (findability): Finding the Digital Story Time episodes was challenging especially on themes and stories as the episodes were labeled as numbers. For the specific episodes, effort had been made to have a contents section 'in this video' that gives specific time stamps for the video but this was not clear and the learners therefore focused on finding the content from watching the episodes, *"I look for the sign language interpreter. I check if there are subtitles first and the pictures. I try to find the story I want. I rewind if I don't understand"* (Tumutumu learner R3)

Impact: YouTube offers most content choice but lacks intuitive organization and discovery features for Deaf users. For example, all the episodes have been labelled by numbers "Digital Story Time episode 029" and missed the opportunity of using themes and stories for ease of remembrance.

3.3.2.4 Reflections on YouTube as a Channel of DST delivery

Based on the analysis of parent survey data, I can make the following inferences about the challenges of using YouTube as a mode of delivery for DST:

Significant Barriers to YouTube Delivery

The data reveals a substantial disconnect between device ownership and reliable internet connectivity that severely limits YouTube as an effective delivery channel:

Device-Connectivity Mismatch: While device ownership is relatively high (90% have smartphones, 26.7% have computers, and 6.7% have tablets), only 6.7% of parents report having consistent internet access. This creates a situation where families possess the necessary hardware for YouTube access but lack the connectivity to use it effectively.

Data Cost Burden: With 73.3% of parents reporting only "occasional internet (e.g., mobile data when needed)" access, this suggests most families rely on prepaid mobile data, which is expensive and used sparingly. This makes streaming video content via YouTube prohibitively costly for regular educational use.

Quality and Reliability Issues: Even among the 6.7% with "regular internet but limited" access, the limitations likely include bandwidth constraints that would make streaming video content difficult, with potential buffering issues that would disrupt the learning experience.

Complete Exclusion: 13.3% of parents report having no internet access whatsoever, meaning YouTube delivery completely fails to reach these families regardless of device ownership.

Technical Proficiency Barriers: 23.3% of parents report difficulty operating the app, suggesting that even with devices and internet, technical proficiency remains a barrier. Additionally, many parents reported in the comments that they need technical training (96.7% requested technical training on using DST).

Implications for DST Strategy

These findings suggest several important implications for the YouTube delivery strategy:

YouTube as Supplementary, Not Primary: YouTube should be positioned as a supplementary, not primary, delivery channel for DST, with television and offline classroom use remaining the core delivery methods.

Offline Solutions Critical: The extremely high demand for offline access to content (86.7% of parents requested this) reflects recognition of the internet connectivity limitations. This reinforces the recommendation for a robust offline content distribution system.

Data-Efficient Design: For YouTube content to be viable, it needs to be optimized for minimal data usage, potentially through lower resolution options, shorter segment lengths, or compressed formats.

Download-and-Watch Model: A system where content can be downloaded once (perhaps at school or other locations with free WiFi) and then watched repeatedly offline would address both the connectivity and cost barriers.

Tiered Content Strategy: Different versions of content could be developed for different bandwidth situations - full multimedia versions for classroom use, and lighter versions for home use with limited connectivity.

In conclusion, while YouTube theoretically offers the most flexible and interactive platform for DST delivery, the reality of the connectivity landscape makes it the least accessible of the three platforms for most families. A successful DST strategy needs to account for this disconnect between device ownership and internet access by developing solutions that minimize dependency on consistent connectivity while maximizing the utility of the devices that families do have.

3.3.3.1 Television Broadcast Effectively Supports Family Engagement

Finding: Television is the most accessible format for family co-viewing, providing important opportunities for Deaf children to share content with hearing family members.

Evidence:

- Family co-viewing common: *"They are both very excited when they are watching the DST in English"* (Kedowa parent R3)
- Sibling involvement: *"When they are all watching, they call you loudly 'Mom, mom, How can I explain to her what this is in sign language'"* (Kedowa parent R6)
- Hearing family members learn from broadcast: *"We learn from the DST"* (Kedowa parent R4)

Impact: Television broadcast effectively supports family viewing and informal sign language acquisition by hearing family members.

3.3.3.2 Fixed Broadcasting Limits Learner Control and Content Access

Finding: The scheduled nature of television broadcast severely limits when and how learners can access DST content, with fixed timing that doesn't accommodate learning needs.

Evidence:

- Length of episodes: The parents feel that the episodes are short and could be a bit longer. *"The KSL episodes are very short time, they show for less than an hour for each episode"* (Tumutumu parent R7). Similar views were expressed by a parent in Kedowa, *"Yes, they should add the time for the stories, some of the stories are just 10minute stories, they should have stories that go to even up to an hour"* (Kedowa, parent 4)
- Airing time slots: Some parents are of the view that the schedule of the programmes should be convenient enough for learners and their parents, *"They should be having the stories in the evenings when we are out of school"* (Tumutumu parent R6)
- DST as a learning opportunity: DST provides learning opportunity for parents to learn sign language as expressed by parent from Kedowa, *"I now know how to communicate with my child" sentiments that were shared with some other parents. However, some parents have only the TV as their only mode of learning sign language and find it too fast for them to learn. They report " the fingerspelling should be incorporated more in the stories and programmes"* (Tumutumu, parent 4) and one recommended telling a whole story through finger spelling, *"They can try to tell a whole story in sign language"* (Tumutumu parent R6)

Impact: Television offers broadest potential reach but suffers from inflexible scheduling and content fragmentation.

3.3.3.3 Content Presentation on Television Needs Optimization

Finding: The current television broadcast format has timing, pacing, and content structure issues that affect comprehension and learning value.

Evidence:

- Timing and pacing concerns: *"The signing part of the stories should be given more time"* (Tumutumu parent R4)
- Content duration concerns: *"Add the time for the stories, some of the stories are just 10minute stories, they should have stories that go to even up to an hour"* (Kedowa parent R4)
- Fixed presentation speed: Cannot adapt to individual learner needs due to broadcast format

Impact: Broadcast format constraints create pacing and timing issues that affect comprehension and learning value.

3.3.3.4 Reflections on Television as DST delivery mode

Feedback and interaction with eKitabu staff notes that the issues raised by the users are already inbuilt in the episodes e.g complete stories, scheduling is available (however this may require parents to be keen because the timings are advertised consistently). The staff were of the opinion that "content presentation is more about the "size" of the TV parents have which we cannot control".

In light of the feedback from eKitabu officer the following are the reflections and insights.

Complete Stories Are Already Included: The general feedback from parents who were part of focus group discussions was that "episodes leave people hanging," which was clarified by the eKitabu team that complete stories are already built into each episode. This suggests the parent perception may stem from other factors such as viewing partial broadcasts or misunderstanding narrative structure.

Scheduling Information Is Already Available: The eKitabu team notes that "timings are advertised consistently," indicating that program scheduling information is already being communicated, though parents may not be "keen" or attentive to these announcements.

Content Presentation Limitations Relate to Home Equipment: The eKitabu team clarifies that presentation issues are primarily related to the "size of the TV parents have," a factor beyond eKitabu's control, rather than the broadcast format itself.

Implications of the Insights

This feedback brings to light various insights that should be noted:

Misalignment Between Implementation and Perception: There appears to be a significant gap between the actual television implementation (complete stories, advertised schedules) and parent/learner perceptions of these elements, suggesting a communication or awareness problem rather than a design problem.

Focus Shifts from Content Design to Awareness Building: The primary challenge may not be redesigning television content but rather ensuring families are fully aware of and utilizing the features already built into the broadcast system.

Equipment Variability as Uncontrollable Factor: The viewing experience limitations attributed to television may be more related to household equipment variance than to the broadcast format itself.

Revised Recommendations for Television Delivery

Given this new understanding, the recommendations shift from content redesign to awareness building and user education:

Enhanced Schedule Communication Strategy: While schedules are being advertised, the methods may need enhancement. Consider multiple channels of communication (school notices, SMS reminders, community announcements) to ensure parents are aware of broadcast times.

Viewing Guide Development: Create simple viewing guides that help parents understand the episode structure and story completion within episodes, addressing the misconception that stories are left incomplete.

Episode Recap Integration: Include brief recaps at the beginning of episodes to help viewers who might have missed previous content, mitigating the impact of fixed scheduling.

Cross-Program Promotion: During DST broadcasts, include announcements about upcoming episodes and times to reinforce schedule awareness.

School-Home Communication Bridge: Utilize schools as a channel to communicate broadcast schedules and episode content to parents, perhaps through weekly schedule handouts.

Conclusion on DST Television Strategy

The findings from user experience highlight that the strategic focus for television users should focus on better communicating its existing features and helping families optimize their viewing experience within the constraints of their home equipment. This approach acknowledges that while eKitabu has limited control over home viewing equipment, they can influence how families understand and engage with the broadcast content.

Television's position in DST delivery confirms it as a strong primary delivery channel for DST, with even greater potential effectiveness once awareness and communication issues are addressed. The core recommendation is therefore strengthening the connection between the well-designed television implementation and family awareness/utilization of its features, rather than fundamentally changing the television content or format

3.3.4. Cross-Platform UX Issues

3.3.4.1 Content Design Preferences Are Consistent Across Platforms

Finding: Users express similar content preferences across all platforms, with strong preferences for shorter stories, multimodal presentation, and age-appropriate content.

Evidence:

- Story length preference consistent across platforms: 5 of 6 Tumutumu learners preferred shorter stories
- Visual content elements valued: Learners cite "animation, sign language" (Kedowa R2) and "videos, sign language" (Kedowa R4) as easy-to-use elements
- Comprehensive content preferred: 51% of surveyed learners preferred "everything in the video (signing, pictures, words, animations)"
- Content type preferences vary by age: Animal content popular with younger learners while people-centered stories appealed to older learners

Impact: Content design principles should remain consistent across platforms while optimizing for platform-specific constraints.

3.3.4.2 Text Presentation Issues Affect Comprehension on All Video Formats

Finding: Text elements (subtitles, captions, and on-screen words) transition too quickly and may be too dense for effective comprehension across all video-based platforms.

Evidence:

- Subtitle timing problems affect all video versions: "Subtitles disappear too quick" (Kedowa parent R6)
- Text density challenges: "Long paragraph" (Kedowa R2) and "difficult words" (Kedowa R4)
- Text-sign coordination important across platforms: "Fingerspelling, constructing of sentences and letters" (Tumutumu parent R5)

Impact: Text presentation issues affect comprehension across all video-based platforms.

4. Platform-Specific Recommendations

4.1. Preloaded Classroom Version Improvements

Schools face unique implementation challenges with limited devices, infrastructure constraints, and curriculum integration needs. These recommendations focus on making DST more effective within these classroom constraints.

4.1.1 Enhance Classroom Access & Control

The current classroom interface doesn't adequately address the different needs of teachers and learners nor does it facilitate effective device sharing. These recommendations aim to maximize limited classroom resources.

a) Develop Teacher/Learner Dual Interface

- *What this means:* Create two different screen layouts – a more advanced one for teachers with features only accessible to teachers and a simpler one for learners that's easier to navigate.
- *Why it matters:* This allows teachers to prepare and control content while still giving learners hands-on experience when devices are available.

4.1.2 Strengthen Curriculum Integration

Teachers consistently report difficulties integrating DST with curriculum requirements and teaching methodologies. These recommendations address the need for better alignment with educational structures.

a) More support for teachers to align DST with teaching methodologies

- *What this means:* Support teachers to know how to effectively integrate the DST videos into the standard teaching approaches like "I do, we do, you do" where concepts are demonstrated, practiced together, then practiced independently.
- *Why it matters:* Teachers currently struggle to incorporate DST into lesson plans because it doesn't follow familiar teaching structures.

b) Support Multi-Grade Adaptation

- *What this means:* Create content variations at different difficulty levels for the same concepts, allowing use from pre-primary through upper grades.
- *Why it matters:* Current content is too simplistic for older learners but still contains valuable concepts they need. The DST user experience seems to be growing organically to higher grades and eKitabu should consider exploring this opportunity.

4.2. YouTube **Version Improvements**

A number of the families access DST through YouTube, but face significant navigation challenges and missed opportunities for family learning. These recommendations address the unique aspects of the YouTube platform experience.

4.2.1 Enhance Navigation & Discovery

The current YouTube experience presents significant barriers for deaf users and their families in finding and controlling content, particularly for those with limited text literacy.

a) Optimize YouTube Channel Architecture

- *What this means:* Reorganize videos into clearly defined playlists with visual thumbnails that show content type, grade level, and subject area.
- *Why it matters:* Current organization makes it nearly impossible for Deaf users to find appropriate content without text search skills.

4.2.2 Support Family Engagement

YouTube viewing often occurs in family settings, creating valuable opportunities for shared learning experiences between deaf children and their family members.

a) Enhance Co-Viewing Features

- *What this means:* Add features designed specifically for family learning, like pause prompts with practice suggestions and simple explanations of signs for hearing family members.
- *Why it matters:* YouTube viewing often happens in family contexts where hearing parents are trying to learn alongside their Deaf child.

b) Facilitate Shared Learning

- *What this means:* Create features that support hearing family members in learning sign language alongside their Deaf child, like optional explanatory content.
- *Why it matters:* Parents report valuable learning experiences when they can understand and participate in DST viewing with their children.

4.3. Television **Broadcast Improvements**

Television remains the most accessible platform for many families but has unique constraints in terms of scheduling, content structure, and viewer control. These recommendations address television's specific challenges.

4.3.1 Optimize **Broadcast Format**

The television viewing experience differs significantly from interactive platforms, requiring specialized content structure and visual design.

a) **Improve Scheduling Communication**

- *What this means:* Find more innovative ways of communicating the programming schedules to parents and learners. This may include having clear, visual program guides showing when DST will air and what content will be featured.
- *Why it matters:* Families need to know when to tune in, especially given the fixed nature of broadcast television.

b) **Enhance Content Presentation**

- *What this means:* Optimize visual layout specifically for television viewing at a distance, with appropriate text size, sign window placement, and visual hierarchy.

Why it matters: Whereas the viewing experience largely depends on the size of the television. It would be important that the design and display of the different components enhances the experience of users. This is because television viewing happens at a distance, often in family rooms, requiring different visual presentation than close-up device viewing.

4.3.2 Support Broadcast Limitations

Television's one-way communication format creates unique challenges that can be addressed through specialized content design.

a) Enhance Content Memorability

- What this means: Design content with strong memory hooks, repetition patterns, and memorable visual frameworks to compensate for lack of replay control.
- Why it matters: Since viewers can't pause or replay broadcast content, it needs to be inherently more memorable.

b) Facilitate Family Participation

- What this means: Include on-screen prompts and activities for family members to engage together during viewing.
- Why it matters: Television is the most common platform for family co-viewing and provides valuable opportunities for communication.

c) Bridge to Other Platforms

- What this means: Expand the references and links to related content available on YouTube or in schools, possibly using QR codes or simple web addresses.
- Why it matters: Creating connections between platforms expands learning opportunities beyond the broadcast limitations. This may also be the opportunity to reference any information for higher grade learners.

4.4 Conclusion

Digital Story Time demonstrates significant potential as a teaching tool for Deaf learners across its three delivery platforms. Each platform presents unique strengths and challenges:

- **Classroom Version** excels in structured learning but faces device limitations and curriculum alignment challenges
- **YouTube Version** offers flexibility and family engagement opportunities but faces connectivity and navigation barriers
- **Television Broadcast** provides broadest accessibility but suffers from scheduling constraints and limited user control

By implementing platform-specific improvements while maintaining consistent design principles and content quality across channels, DST can become a more effective educational resource that bridges school and home learning environments.

The prioritized recommendations in this report focus on addressing the unique constraints of each platform while capitalizing on their respective strengths to create a more engaging, effective, and accessible DST experience for all stakeholders. Implementing these recommendations will strengthen DST's value proposition as an essential educational tool for Deaf learners in Kenya and beyond.

Annexes

Annex 1: The User Experience Data Collection Process

Procedure used during User Experience data collection

Participant: Learner

Support: Teachers provided signing interpretation during the interview process.

Learner Selection: Fair distribution across all classes, with a higher representation from lower primary grades due to their higher engagement in the program. (it was a random selection)

Part 1: Emoji Reactions

For each of the following, the learner was shown the described visual and asked to select one of five emojis (sad, happy, confused, excited, bored) to represent their reaction. They were then asked to explain their choice.

- DST App/LOGO: Shown a photo of the DST logo.
- Person Signing: Shown a short video clip of a person signing from DST Episode 029.
- Story Characters: Shown a short video clip of story characters from DST Episode 029.
- Using at School: Shown a photo of a learner using DST at school.
- Using at Home: Shown a photo of a child using DST at home alone.

Part 2: "Show Me How" Activity

The learner was asked the following questions:

- Can you use DST?
- Which devices can you use to watch DST? (Mention if you can use them without help or support from anyone).

Part 3: Sticker Ranking

For each item in this section, the learner was given five star stickers and shown a short video clip to rate.

- Signing Person: Short video clip of a person signing from DST Episode 029.
- Pictures/Animations: Short video clip of pictures and animations from DST Episode 029.
- Words/Text: Short video clip of text/words of animals from DST Episode 029.
- Stories/Characters: Short video clip of a story from DST Episode 029.
- Games/Activities: Short video clip of person activities from DST Episode 029.

Part 4: Drawing Activity

The learner was provided with blank paper and a pencil and asked to draw or write anything that excites them when watching DST. After drawing/writing, they were asked to explain what they drew or wrote.

Part 5: Choice Questions

For each of the following, the learner was shown pictures representing the two options and asked to choose their preference and explain why.

Story Length:

SHORT STORIES / LONG STORIES- showed them a picture of both long and short story and asked them to choose and explain their preference choice.

Watching Style:

ALONE / WITH FRIENDS showed them a picture of both learner watching alone and watching with friend's story and asked them to choose and explain their preference choice

Content Type:

PEOPLE STORIES / ANIMAL STORIES - showed them a picture of both people and animal stories and asked them to choose and explain their preference choice.

Device Preference:

TABLET / COMPUTER / PHONE / TV- showed learner a picture of each item below and asked them to choose and explain their choice.

Part 6: Facilitator Observations

The facilitator rated the learner based on their observations and provided explanations.

Overall Engagement Level:

- Very engaged
- Somewhat engaged
- Neutral
- Somewhat disengaged
- Very disengaged

Communication Confidence:

- Very confident
- Somewhat confident
- Neutral
- Somewhat hesitant
- Very hesitant

Annex 2: User Journeys

These simplified journey maps capture the key elements of the user experience across all three platforms. The satisfaction curve is indicated with unhappy, Overall satisfied, or Very Happy ratings at each stage to show the emotional journey.

For content selection, the examples used in “experiences” and “customer expectations” talk about “device availability” rather than the teacher knowledge on content itself and linking it to lessons”

DST - Classroom Version User Journey

Stages of Journey	Teacher Preparation	Content Selection	Classroom Introduction	Guided Viewing	Interactive Practice	Independent Application
Activities	Teacher reviews DST to find materials matching curriculum 					
Feelings						
Very Happy						
Overall Satisfied						
Unhappy						
Experiences	“Content should be a bit higher for adaption at primary level”	“Two classes need gadgets at the same time and they are not enough”	“I use DST mainly for storytelling and concept reinforcement”	“They can interact with gadgets from morning to evening”	“They come in front of the class. They just start role playing”	“Only teacher do the operation on the gadget”
Customer Expectations	Content organized by curriculum and grade level	Sufficient devices for all learners	Engaging concept introduction	Clear visuals and appropriate pacing	Structured practice opportunities	Direct interaction with devices

DST - Youtube Version User Journey

Stages of Journey	Content Discovery	Selection & Start	3) Individual/Family Viewing	4) Pause & Practice	5) Content Completion	6) Related Content Exploration
Activities	Search for DST content on Youtube	Choose video based on thumbnail	Watch content (individually or with family)	Pause video to practice signs	Finish watching content (review the learning)	Try to find related content
Feelings						
Very Happy						
Overall Satisfied						
Unhappy						
Experiences	"I look for the sign language interpreter. I check if there are subtitles"	"I search for the title I want to watch."	"My child is the one who teaches me the sign language"	"When we are watching with the kid, we pause, and then we repeat the signing"	"The child will ask you your name, write it and then sign it"	Limited suggestions for Deaf learners
Customer Expectations	Visual organization of content	Clear thumbnails showing content type	Clear signing and engaging visuals	Easy playback controls	Clear conclusion of learning	Clear suggestions for next content

DST - Television Broadcast Version User Journey

Stages of Journey	Teacher Preparation	Content Selection	Classroom Introduction	Guided Viewing	Interactive Practice	Independent Application
Activities	Try to discover when the programs will air	Gather to watch as a family	Watch at broadcast pace without controls	Process information without replay option	Talk about content with family	Wait for next broadcast
Feelings						
Very Happy						
Overall Satisfied						
Unhappy						
Experiences	"KSL episodes are very short time, less than an hour"	"Very excited when watching the DST"	"Subtitles disappear too quick"	"Some episodes leave people hanging"	"Mom, how can I explain to her what this is in sign language"	"Should have stories in the evenings when we are out of school"
Customer Expectations	Clear program schedule	Clear introduction of content	Appropriate pacing for viewers	Complete stories with conclusions	Content that prompts discussion	Information about upcoming content

Report

Prepared **By**

FoVET Research & Consultancy

+254 728 513129

info@fovet.co

www.fovet.co

Nairobi West, P.O Box 6732-00200 Kenya

